

CHARACTERISTICS AND ANALYSIS OF INTELLECTUAL NOVELS IN LITERATURE

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Abstract:

Background. It is well known that literature is a genre that is relative in terms of its purpose, related to their art. Fiction, as a complex synthesis of art forms, is constantly updated and perfected throughout its development; just artistic Word fans have come up with unexpected ideas, themes, forms, and contents that have caught the attention of many fields.

Methods. Word fans have come up with unexpected ideas, themes, forms, and contents that have caught the attention of many fields, not just philosophy, politics, sociology, psychology, and even the exact sciences, such as medicine. Albert Einstein, the founder of the universal theory of relativity, acknowledges the great importance that the works of Fyodor Dostoevsky played in the realization of his discovery. Homer's Iliad, Firdavsi's Shahnameh, Dante's Divine Comedy, Zahriddin Bobur's Boburnoma, Goethe's Faust, Tolstoy's War and Peace, Dostoevsky's Crime and Punishment, Chingiz Aitmatov's The Signs of the End Times There are still differences, sometimes even contradictions.

Results. At the modern stage of the development of fiction, the intellectual novel genre emerged. The term "intellectual novel" was first coined by the German writer Thomas Mann in the early twentieth century. "The historical and global devastation of 1914-1923 exacerbated the need to understand the period in the minds of contemporary people with unprecedented intensity and overthrew this literature. This process blurred the boundaries between science and art; the thought-provoking idea gave life to a living, heart-pounding idea, gave life to plastic images, and created a type of book that could be called an "intellectual novel.

Conclusion. ." What we call an intellectual novel, in its course, T. Mann and G. Gesse, R. Muzil and G. Brox, M. Bulgakov and K. Chapek, U. Faulkner and T. Wolf, P. Koelo and Ch. Yes, the synthesis of philosophy and art, science and fiction is the main feature of an intellectual novel .This synthesis was manifested in the growth of mythological thinking in the artistic reincarnation of the historical period, in the perception of myths as a universal model of human life and a recurring law, going beyond the mere symbolic framework.

Keywords: Fiction, philosophy, politics, sociology, psychology, mythological thinking, magical realism, mythological scientific achievements, intellectual novel, national literature.

Introduction. A complex synthesis of art forms, is constantly updated and perfected throughout its development; just artistic works have come up with unexpected ideas, themes, forms, and contents that have caught the attention of many fields, not just philosophy, politics, sociology, psychology, and even the exact sciences, such as medicine. The vast expanse of the artistic chronotope, the change of the text of the historical period, the merciless bright scenes of the existing reality through innumerable analogies and parallels and its deep perception as a whole, the abundance of philosophical ideas make the examples of intellectual the highest artistic and philosophical thinking. This type of genre began to appear in our national literature as well. Writers such as Khurshid Dostmammad, Nazar Eshanqul, Ulugbek Hamdam, I sajon Sultan boldly, used the experience of intellectual. event. just artistic unexpected ideas, themes, forms, and contents that have caught the attention of many fields, not just philosophy, politics, sociology, psychology, and even the exact sciences, such as medicine. Albert Einstein, the founder of the universal theory of relativity, acknowledges the great importance that the works of Fyodor Dostoevsky played in the realization of his discovery.

Materials and methods. This is a national intellectual

- Artistic reflection of the Eastern-philosophical worldview:
 - The artistic "rebirth" of the primitive religious-mythological imagination, which is radically different from the West
- The level of artistic and philosophical thinking, the attitude of writers to humanity and existence, the period, formed in different historical, socio-political environments, except in the West;
- the centuries
- long psychological pressure, the manifestation of the people's thinking in the form of a, in the

person of a certain writer, who is trying to get rid of the complications of the spiritual invasion

Therefore, as an independent nation and country, we can say that the intellectual is the brightest example of national identity. According to the above, the fundamental scientific study of the national intellectual in comparison with world literature plays an important role not only in the field of art and fiction, but also in defining our place as a nation in the world. The relevance and necessity of the study of the subject arises, in addition to the interests of pure art and literature, primarily from the historical social need characterized by the above. So far, this topic has not been studied fundamentally scientifically in our literature. The life and work of the world-famous Irish writer Oscar Wilde (1854 -1900) was a tragic full of

contradictions.

The of Oscar Wilde, a brilliant speaker and great writer, has always been in the spotlight of world literary critics, and many different monographs, dissertations and articles have been created

on the life and work of the writer, including biographical works from the JZL series. The life and work of O. Wilde B. Show, A. Jid, A. Morua, A. Kamyu, Ya. Parandovsky, T. Mann, H.L. Borges did not escape the attention of world-famous writers.

At the same time, he did not

leave indifferent Russian writers such as L. Tolstoy, A. Gorky, K. Pustovsky. Although it has attracted the attention of hundreds of researchers at various levels, from the world's most

famous scientists, it is probably his complex life and controversial work. The problem of novelism has been consistently studied in Uzbek literature, including the work of Isajon Sultan,

which has been scientifically evaluated by literary critics at various. Word fans have come up with unexpected ideas, themes, forms, and contents that have caught the attention of many fields, not just philosophy, politics, sociology, psychology, and even the exact sciences, such as medicine. Albert Einstein, the founder of the universal theory of relativity, acknowledges the great importance that the works of Fyodor Dostoevsky played in the realization of his discovery. Homer's Iliad, Firdavsi's Shahnameh, Dante's Divine Comedy, Zahriddin Bobur's Boburnoma, Goethe's Faust, Tolstoy's War and Peace, Dostoevsky's Crime and Punishment, Chingiz Aitmatov's The Signs of the End Times There are still differences, sometimes even contradictions.

levels of research.

Oscar Wilde's Dorian Gray is a highly artistic synthesis of realism, magical realism, the achievements of mythological science, and other forms of art. Anyone who has read the over and over again will come to the conclusion that the protagonist, Dorian Gray, faces himself mercilessly at the mysterious portrait painted by his

friend Basil at his request. It is as if a coup is taking place in his inner world. However, Gray cannot overcome the satanic feeling within himself. He doesn't want her to do that. He is a tragic victim of his own mismanagement. Gray sums up his past sins by looking at his portrait .D. Gray, who is adorned with the world,

falls in love at this moment and meets the beautiful Sibyl, and the love ends in tragedy. That is; realizing that the girl was pregnant with a child, he drowned her and

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committed a brutal murder. Gray also has an affection for the environment. So Dorian Gray begins to take matters into his own hands, and eventually takes a dagger

with a picture of his beloved and tries to bribe him. But at that moment, a creature

appears in the portrait (magical realism) and eats Gray. This is a sign of the evil of the devil's lust, which has always saved Jesus. The portrait of Dorian Gray is one of the most sensational works in the literary world.

Incorporating elements

of miraculous realism, this work sheds light on the spiritual crisis of Dorian Gray, a beautiful

20-year old beauty. Although the plot is unusual for the nineteenth century, it is ideologically similar

to many works. In the last century, readers have confessed that he was a justly punished, tempted sinner. Today's reader, on the other hand, recognized

Dorian Gray as an arrogant, helpless, and weak hero who sacrificed his entire being, heart, and

soul for eternal youth. Born into a family of cyborgs, Dorian, who possessed the beauty of onameros, was faced with the cruel judgment of fate when he had ample opportunity to live

happily ever after

“There is always some tragedy hidden behind something beautiful. In order for the smallest and most insignificant flower to bloom, the worlds must suffer the pain of childbirth,”

said one of the protagonists. Indeed, behind the beautiful image of Dorian Gray

lies a great tragedy: the soul dies, the soul disappears forever. Dirty brothels, continuous living, theft, the ugliness of the chaos in society are now a beauty in his mind, and such vices are a

constant need. Oscar Wilde brought to literature the image of a hero of such a complex nature, and through it he showed with great artistic skill the limits of human desires, the consequences of the disturbance of the balance of life. And the work won the hearts of millions, and the

image of Dorian Gray was written in the reader's notebook. One of the topics Wilde tries to discuss using the plot is whether it is possible to change human nature. Was the book the cause of the changes in Dorian after reading the book sent by Lord Henry, or were there already such

bad

qualities in his nature? Can an ugly person who has completely lost his conscience be

“restored” by good deeds, or are all his actions based on ambition? It is certainly very difficult, if not impossible, to answer these questions. The play also discusses what art is, how it should

be, whether ancestral traditions are appropriate for generations, and a number of other similar

topics. Lord Henry, who pioneered the doctrine of hedonism, believed that the only purpose of human life should be madness, peace. In his opinion, every new day is another opportunity to

enjoy. As Shakespeare's Hamlet said,

"If a man's greatest desires are to eat and sleep, how can

he be different from an animal?" So our heroes are no different from animals either. For the most part, are dedicated to narrating individual experiences of characters, creating a closer,

more complex portrait of these characters and the world they live in. Inner feelings and thoughts, as well as complex, even conflicting ideas or values are typically explored in, more so than

in preceding forms of literature. It's not just the stories themselves that are more personal,

but the experience of reading them as well. Where epic poetry and similar forms of storytelling

were designed to be publicly read or consumed as an audience, are geared more towards an individual reader. The following traits must be present for a work to be considered :

Written in prose, as opposed to verse. Narrators may have different degrees of knowledge or

different points of view (first person versus third person and so on). While stylized such as

epistolary do exist, the key distinction here is between prose and verse.

Results and discussion. At the modern stage of the development of fiction, the novel genre

emerged. The term "novel" was first coined by the German writer Thomas Mann in the early

twentieth century. "The historical and global devastation of 1914-1923 exacerbated the need to

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understand the period in the minds of contemporary people with unprecedented intensity and

overthrew this literature. This process blurred the boundaries between science and art; the thought-provoking idea gave life to a living, heart-pounding idea, gave life to plastic images, and

created a type of book that could be called an "novel." What we call an novel, in its course,

T. Mann and G. Gesse, R. Muzil and G. Brox, M. Bulgakov and K. Chapek, U. Faulkner and T. Wolf, P. Koelo and Ch. Yes, the synthesis of philosophy and art, science and fiction is the main feature of an novel. Remember, for example, the famous German writer Goethe's tragedy Faust. Faust, like Gray, who "sold his heart to the devil

(Mephistopheles) in order to acquire unimaginable knowledge, to taste endless worldly pleasures, and to be alone with Margarita, suffers a spiritual decline. Or the American writer T.

mentioned above. Take Clyde Griffiths, the protagonist of Dreyzer's the American Tragedy.

Clyde, who sold his conscience to gain wealth, a career, and a beautiful girl, also suffers a conscience like Gray at the end of the play.

Although the plot of the work is unusual for the

nineteenth century, it is ideologically similar to many works. Remember, for example, the famous German writer Goethe's tragedy Faust. Faust, like Gray, who "sold his heart to the devil

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writer T. mentioned above. Take Clyde Griffiths, the protagonist of Dreyzer's The American Tragedy. Dorian, Basil, Lord Henry are the three central protagonists of the work. Dorian – easel

painted gray (canvas). The cloth is white, and Lord Henry is black. If you want to paint

using white and black, the result will be a gray quality colored artwork. If the same amount of black paint is added to a drop of white paint, the white color will definitely be contaminated.

The protagonist of our story was shaped in the same way as a person: Bezil's "white" advice could not overcome Lord Henry's "black" teachings. The American academic Peter H. Smith describes the of Latin

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America as people from an identifiable social class, who have been conditioned by that common experience and thus are inclined to share a set of common

assumptions (values and ethics); that ninety-four per cent of come either from the middle class or from the upper class and that

only six per cent come from the working class. Philosopher

Steven Fuller said that because cultural capital confers power and social status as a status

group they must be autonomous in order to be credible as : (Basil about Dorian)"He has stood

as Paris in dainty armour, and as Adonis with huntsman's cloak and polished boar-spear.

Crowned with heavy lotus blossoms, he has sat on the prow of Adrian's barge, looking into

the green, turbid Nile. He has leaned over the still pool of some Greek woodland, and seen in

the water's silent silver the wonder of his own beauty." (Lord Henry describes "fidelity")

"It has nothing to do with our own will. It is either an unfortunate accident, or an unpleasant result of temperament." "You don't mean to say that Basil has got any passion or any romance in

him?"

"I don't know whether he has any passion, but he certainly has romance," said Lord

Henry, with an amused look in his eyes. "Has he never let you know that?"

"Never.

I must ask him about it. I am rather surprised to hear it." (Basil Hallward described)

"Rugged and straightforward as he was, there was something in his nature that was purely feminine in its tenderness." (Basil to Dorian)

"It is quite true that I have worshipped you with far

more romance of feeling than a man usually gives to a friend. Somehow, I had never loved a

woman. I suppose I never had time. Perhaps, as Harry says, a really grande passion is the privilege of those who have nothing to do, and that is the use of the idle classes in a country." (Basil confronts Dorian)"Dorian, Dorian, your reputation is infamous. I know you and Harry are great

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friends. I say nothing about that now, but surely you need not have made his sister's name a by-word."

(The first part of this passage was deleted from the 1890 magazine text; the second part of the passage was inserted to the 1891 novel text.) Anti-

intellectualism is hostility to and

mistrust of intellect, and intellectualism, commonly expressed as deprecation of education

and philosophy and the dismissal of art, literature, and science as impractical, politically

motivated, and even contemptible human pursuits. Anti-intellectuals present themselves and are

perceived as champions of common folk—populists against political and academic elitism—

and tend to see educated people as a status class that dominates political discourse and higher

education while being detached from the concerns of ordinary people. In the U.S., the American conservative economist Thomas Sowell argued for distinctions between unreasonable and reasonable wariness of their influence upon the institutions of a society. In defining as "people whose occupations deal primarily with ideas", they are different from people whose work

is the practical application of ideas. That cause for layman mistrust lies in the incompetence

outside their fields of expertise. Although possessed of great working knowledge in their specialist fields, when compared to other professions and occupations, the members of society face little

discouragement against speaking authoritatively beyond their field of formal expertise, and thus are unlikely to face responsibility for the social and practical consequences of their errors.

Hence, a physician is judged competent by the effective treatment of the sickness of a patient, yet might face a medical malpractice lawsuit should the treatment harm the patient. In contrast, a tenured university professor is unlikely to be judged competent or incompetent by the

effectiveness of his or her intellectualism (ideas), and thus not face responsibility for the

social and practical consequences of the implementation of the ideas, e.g. the Chicago Boys and the Military dictatorship of Chile (1973–90).

Conclusion. The synthesis of philosophy and art, science and fiction is the main feature of the novel. This synthesis was manifested in the growth of mythological thinking in the artistic reincarnation of the historical period, in the perception of myths as a universal model of human life and a recurring law, going beyond the mere figurative sphere. Fiction, as a complex synthesis of art forms, is constantly updated and perfected throughout its development; not only artistic just collect them. Another example is Raphael in French author Honoré de Balzac's. The Magic of the Blind Skin. The fulfillment of desires; Dorian decides to live the last months of his life relying on his conscience, just as a young man who has risked his life for infinite wealth and luxury realizes that at the end of the work he is no different from an animal if he constantly satisfies human desires (or needs). Effectively so, that is precisely the specific function of them: To treat everyone else as if they, too, were. That is to say, to not attempt to hypnotise them, to intimidate them, or to seduce them, but to awaken in them the mechanism of intelligence that weighs, evaluates, and comprehends. One must start from the Socratic premise that everyone in the world reveals himself, herself intelligent when treated as if intelligent. Is that social function compatible with the offices of politicians? Because, more often than not, they tend to govern themselves by the cynical principle that: "One must not treat the public as if they were imbeciles, nor forget that they are imbeciles", which was established by the novelist Frédéric Beigbeder (who, not in vain, began his career as an advertising man); it is plainly obvious that those are opposite approaches. What is bad, is that the first approach demands effort from the interlocutors—attention, reflection, and dubious sizing up, while the second approach flatters the primitive emotions of enthusiasm or revenge, and converts critical thinking to satire or to swearing curses, and social problems into notorious scandal. The contemporary understanding of history emerged

in the immediate postwar period of the 1940s, in its earlier incarnation as “the history of ideas” under the leadership of Arthur Lovejoy, the founder of the Journal of the History of Ideas. Since that time, Lovejoy’s formulation of “unit-ideas” was developed in different and divergent directions, such as contextualize, Historically sensitive accounts of activity in the corresponding historical period, which investigative shift is reflected in the replacement of the term “history of ideas” with the term “history”.

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